

Leadership Decision Making

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Forewords

“Think 100 times before you take a decision, But once that decision is taken, stand by it as one man. - Muhammad Ali Jinnah”

Decision making in organizational leadership in public and private activities can involve the future of a Nation or a just an organization. In the area of conducting the National Defence, Financial, Corporate Management, Education, Health and Ambient, all converge to the sustainability of an organization, or a country and even of Mankind. This Paperwork will help the reader to understand the responsibility on the effects and performance that a Leader decision has in Space and Time.

Concept

A concept to be considered initially is that one of Taylor in the 20th century, in which the scientific bases of management are of a technological nature. It is believed that the best way to increase production is by improving the techniques or methods used by employees. With this theory, Taylor treated employees as machines that could be manipulated by their leaders.

Another theory of scientific management is related to the development of an organization in the most rational way possible, to create efficiency in management and increase production.

There was a reformulation and restructuring of functions to obtain greater efficiency, satisfying the economic interests of workers through various incentive plans. Clearly, here, the role of the leader is to establish and enforce performance criteria to meet the organization's objectives.

The role of the leader is to pay attention to the organization as a whole and not to the people who were there.

In 1925, the trend towards Mayo's theory was born, which began to replace those patterns by the human relations movement.

More attention is being given to human relations, in addition to seeking, through the best technological methods, to increase production. It begins to support the idea that the real centers of power in an organization were interpersonal relationships, which develop within the work unit.

Thus, the theory that the role of the leader was to facilitate the cooperative achievement of objects among the followers, came to be considered, providing opportunities for their personal growth and development and personal needs become the focus.

In short: The scientific management movement emphasizes the concern with the "task" (production), while the human relations movement highlights the concern with the "human relations" (people). With the combination of these two concerns, new theories on Leadership were structured.

Some faces of these theories begin to be studied, as is the case of Tannenbaum's theory (1970), which speaks of the styles adopted by the leaders.

This and other authors of the time spoke of autocratic and democratic leaders, stating that, before these studies, they were defined as autocratic, because they were much more concerned with production. They need to inform how their employees should act, determining what to do and how to carry out the task.

Democratic, on the other hand, is considered the least directive style, which accentuates concerns about human relations, allowing employees to share their responsibilities with their leader, involving them in the planning and execution of tasks.

The choice of leadership style must take into account what the leader thinks about his power of authority and about human nature.

- The autocratic leader theory is based on the idea that his behaviour is due to the position he occupies and because he understands that people are lazy and irresponsible.

- The democratic leader theory assumes that people can basically self-manage, as long as they are properly accompanied to produce motivation.

The choice of leadership style has some increasing variations in attitudes, which develop from the leader to those developed by the employees, no longer having the rigid conception that he is only autocratic or only democratic.

The Evolution of Leadership Theory

It can be said that when it comes to leadership theory, it is possible to find several ways to study what leadership means. One is that discussed by Peter Drucker (1999), according to which «leadership is a matter of how to be, not how to do it. We spend a

good part of our lives learning how to do things, but in the end it is the quality and individual character that define great leaders ».

As for the leaders, the author states that «(...) they prosper through the efforts of the people they lead. The basic task of a leader is to form a highly productive and motivated workforce ».

For Drucker, the leader has challenges to overcome until he reaches a cohesive community that is thus structured inside and outside his organization so that one can «(...) invest in relationships and transmit a vision that establishes communication between a workforce and a varied market ». The author argues that a leader is one who cares about what is around him, near or far, inside or outside the organization, and that the true leader understands that his worker is inserted in a difficult world and will not be committed to performance organization. The leader, then, will have to have circular relationships in his organization, since people want to participate in the cause and the effect brought about by the actions taken. The leader must propose an exit from the common scope and enter a larger sphere where people realize that they are being observed and valued for the ideas they are exposing. This is where spaces for intelligent and creative people are born to express themselves and produce more than they already did.

In Tannenbaum's (1973) definition, leadership is an "interpersonal influence exercised in a situation and directed, through the communication process, towards the achievement of specific objectives". For Koontz (1973) leadership is about influencing people to achieve a common goal. Paulson's (1994) theory states that "leadership is the activity of influencing people by making them voluntarily engage in group objects". Drucker (1999) says that a leader is one who takes care of his employees observing their peculiarities, differentiating the way they deal with each one of them. It is useless to give a task together if the potential is different: one will produce more, the other less. It takes a good leader to realize that employees have different qualities and needs.

Another important aspect to detect a good leader is the establishment of the goals to be achieved, and, for that, the leader will have to think about the individuality, as well as the development potential of his employee, so that he can determine what will be the best task to be assigned to each of the team members.

The leader who manages to have a good perception of his employee must also think about the goal that will be defined for the company's growth based on the definition of the goals to be achieved by this employee.

The goal is defined from the previous income with the proposal to increase the workload, so that the employee's potential can be fully utilized. The target can be

modified with each new assessment, as the employee (individual) is not in a static position in the company.

Drucker (1999) argues that the leader must review what is done, being a way of giving the employee a satisfaction of what is being achieved with the work developed and, if necessary, reformulating, to improve performance in tasks. The employee must state his point of view; thus, it is possible to make a general balance, that is, the team members will put their ways of seeing the work, allowing adjustments that can facilitate the development of the task.

The role of the leader is to analyze the employee's vision and from there formulate and reformulate the ideas that arise from this exchange of information.

Also according to the same author, a person learns more when he teaches, and it can be understood that the manager, when using his ability to teach, is practicing his way of exposing what he knows, exercising and opening the possibility of verifying whether these shapes are correct. From this exhibition, doubts and suggestions may arise from those who learn, effectively offering the greatest knowledge to those who teach. It also serves to make him understand that in teaching he "strengthens" himself, improving his way of teaching.

The leader can check the quantity and quality of what he exposes from what he has learned previously and the more he does this activity the more he will learn. The leader becomes better when he exercises his power to teach and will be more productive if he has as his subordinates people with different characteristics, also having the advantage of improvement by repeating this act, acquiring knowledge and experience for continuous improvement.

Another characteristic of the leader refers to the respect given to him. An irrelevant situation is that it does not matter whether the employee likes him or not or vice versa; that is not the point. What is expected is that out of respect there is the possibility of awakening in the employee the confidence necessary for the task to be carried out with sufficient proficiency and with that the leader gives due recognition to the work.

Most management theories indicate that the definition of what leadership is and is based on a process of influencing the activity of an individual, or a group, to pursue an objective in a given situation.

Situational leadership

Situational leadership emphasizes, among other things, the importance of the leader's diagnostic ability to influence people, or even the ability to be effective where he is

seen as the person who adapts his leader's behavioural style to the needs of the followers and situations.

This is the differential of this theory.

As the situations are not constant, the use of an appropriate style of leadership behaviour is a challenge for those who want to consider themselves a good leader and become effective.

If the skills and motives of the people who are subordinate to him are so variable, the leader must be sensitive to the diagnosis, feeling and appreciating the differences found.

In other words, managers must be able to identify the reality of their environment. But, even with good diagnostic skills, leaders will not be effective if they do not know how to adapt their leadership style to the demands of the environment.

The leader must have the personal flexibility and the range of skills necessary to vary his behaviour. If the needs and motives of your employees are different, they must be treated differently (Hersey and Blanchard (1986)). The same authors comment that it is easy to say that managers should apply the theory and results of behavioural research in the development of diagnostic skills, necessary to maximize their effectiveness - the difficult thing is to put this into practice. The question of diagnosis and the ability to be an effective leader are made possible by applying the theory of situational leadership.

Leadership: Style and Style Change

The style to be adopted to lead is a factor that contributes for the leadership to be structured correctly to obtain a positive result. The leadership style developed by the leader requires time to materialize and will depend on experience and training. According to Tannenbaum (1973), four internal forces can be observed to influence the leadership style:

- the value system: degree of firmness that the leader understands as necessary to make the employee participate in the decisions to be made or by his understanding of how important it is for a given employee to take responsibility for the decision;
- trust in employees: knowing how to put the decision in the hands of employees and having the confidence that the result will be satisfactory, knowing that among these employees are lazy and irresponsible employees or, on the contrary, motivated and creative employees; also be confident because he understands that there is knowledge and competence in the area of responsibility that he is indicating;

- leadership inclination: these are the different types assumed by the leader; he may have a predominant style, that is, the "boss" type, who likes group work with the employee or who delegates and lets the employee make the decision he sees as the most appropriate;

- feeling of security in uncertain situations: it has a great impact on the manager's willingness to give control over the decision-making process to others.

Taking into account the expectations regarding the followers, the superiors, the peers themselves and the organization it can be said that these are variables that interfere in the position that the leader will assume.

Other situational variables that are part of the influence on the decision are those related to the job requirement, time and external environment.

The task behaviour that appears in the chart relates to the way the leader acts with his subordinate, saying when, where and how to do the task.

Relationship behaviour is the way that the leader finds to communicate efficiently, making it possible to exchange information, thereby causing a relationship based on support and encouragement. The leader must be willing to actually listen to what the employee has to say.

It has specific zones that are related between maturity and the two ways of acting by the leader, task and relationship behaviour. For each of these levels of maturity, the correct application of task and relationship behaviour is necessary.

The leadership style can be divided into four items.

- DETERMINE: directly used for people with low maturity. This profile is characteristic of people who have neither the capacity nor the desire to take responsibility for carrying out tasks. This can be generated by insecurity about the task. The person who presents this type of maturity must be supervised; that is why the word "determine" is used for this level of maturity. This style is due to high task behaviour and low relationship behaviour.

- PERSUADE: defined for people with a low to moderate maturity; they are unable to do the job, but they are willing to take responsibility; is a person who trusts you. In this adopted style, direction is still given for the task to be performed and a little support (relationship behaviour) to emphasize its demonstrated willingness.

The leader uses the "persuade" style to get the team to adopt the behaviour they want, this through more open communication making them feel free to express what they are feeling in relation to the accomplishment of the task. Team members accept

the decision better when they understand its reason; for this reason, style calls for the leader to behave in a high task and a high relationship.

Argyris (1975), when discussing the function of the ego and self-concept, refers that the team member includes in his own behaviour much more security and an increase in his potential to understand it. So, it is clear that the support given by the leader helps the team member to acquire more security, if their leader favours relationship behaviour, giving the team member the opportunity to know the reactions of the communication and consequently form their own concept, they will become much safer.

- SHARE: style suitable for followers between moderate and high maturity. Here the team member has capacity, but his disposition is diminished by his lack of security in himself when necessary to assume responsibility.

The consequence of this is that the leader should emphasize relationship behaviour, maintaining open communication to create a motivating atmosphere, transmitting security and finally developing the task. In this way, it is possible to summarize the characteristics that the employee can present through the correct application of this type of leadership style, which are:

a) Making the employee feel safe and

b) Monitoring the accomplishment of the task that he already knows how to perform. That is, he will make the decisions with the leader, due to the good communication established. The relationship is high and the task is low.

- DELEGATE: for leaders with high maturity, capable and willing. The leader will give the direction in a small dose, as well as the support dose, in other words, neither task behaviour nor relationship behaviour will be small.

The leader can identify the problem, but it is the responsibility of getting the problem solved, they will decide how and when to do it to obtain a satisfactory result.

In this way, we can summarize the leadership styles mentioned, as follows:

Style 1: The leader directs his employee. The leader provides specific instructions and strictly supervises the fulfilment of tasks.

Style 2: The leader trains before demanding. The leader continues to direct and supervise tasks, but also explains decisions and encourages development.

Style 3: The leader supports decisions. The leader facilitates and supports employees' efforts to accomplish tasks and share decision-making with them.

Style 4: The leader delegates tasks to the employee. The leader transfers responsibility for decision making and problem solving to employees.

Maturity

The concept of maturity in situational leadership can be defined as the stage of growth where the human being has the necessary capacity and disposition to take their actions, direct their own behaviour and be able to assume responsibilities (Hersey & Blanchard).

The human being can advance or regress in some moments depending on stimuli, influencing both at work and outside and occurring at all times.

A stimulus can be more clearly perceived in the opportunity to perform tasks that are new or different from those performed with a certain frequency.

It can be said, then, that the individual cannot be considered mature or immature in the total sense; he may develop a task well, however, in others it may be totally ineffective, which does not mean that he is immature. It all depends on your degree of encouragement to accomplish what you are proposing.

In order to find a solution to this issue of inefficiency, the task monitoring criterion can be adopted so that the manager transmits the necessary knowledge and makes the employee more secure by this given stimulus.

This exposed theory is the one indicated by the studies of situational leadership, which is divided into two types: psychological maturity and maturity for work.

Psychological Maturity

The concept defined by Hersey & Blanchard (1986) about psychological maturity is described by the willingness or motivation to perform a task. If the leader provides favourable conditions, his employee will be well targeted and in the right way.

The authors say that psychological maturity is about self-confidence and commitment. This illustrates the idea of psychological maturity, because if he is stimulated, he will be confident in himself.

This concept shows that the more the leader directs the relationship behaviour of this team member without overloading him, the more he is motivated, acquiring trust and thus, maturing, producing positive effects for the manager and the company.

Psychological maturity is the ability to trust, to be motivated, to be willing to perform a task. This occurs with the individual when he matures over time. It moves from a passive state to a growing state of activity, and it can progressively structure its independence.

The age of the individual is a considerable factor, but it is not a determining factor for perceiving psychological maturity in development, as can be seen from the study of situational leadership.

The importance is not in chronological age, but in psychological age.

For a work to be developed, it is not possible to simply analyze psychological maturity by itself: one must analyze the entire context of the task that will be developed and the variables so that it is done in the best way. What cannot be done is to disconnect these two points. As important as the analysis of psychological maturity is the analysis of the context. With this reference, the manager can rely on making the best management decision for the led employee. To speak of growth in maturity, one can study Argyris (1975), who states: "growth means development in the components and in our particular world". This phrase is intended to demonstrate how the influence of particular events that occur in everyday life affects personality growth. This growth is due not only to new elements, but to elements that enrich existing ones. This is called the ripening process.

The leader who is concerned with particular growth, consequently, is providing greater conditions for the maturation of his team. He must think about developing the various components of the personality, so that there can be global development, which includes, therefore, the working environment where he is.

Maturity for Work

It is considered that it is the capacity that the team member has to perform a task that involves their technical knowledge. People with high maturity carry out their duties without the need for assistance; in contrast, people with low maturity for work need a lot of technical direction to develop the requested task (Argyris, 1975).

Maturity for work is related to how to develop the task. It can be improved by the training that the manager will have to offer.

Technical knowledge and technical capacity are the two requirements to obtain the maturity for the job. When the employee has high maturity, the manager will be achieving his goal, as he will be carrying out his task by delegating powers, after completing three stages.

According to Situational Leadership, there are three stages:

- 1) determine (low maturity);
- 2) persuade (moderately low maturity); and
- 3) sharing (moderately high maturity).

The next stage is the delegation stage, where the manager already gets some decisions from the employee, revealing a high maturity for the job.

The team member needs to assume an orderly growth as his objective; the leader will not be able to transmit too much knowledge so that he does not lose the focus of his good development and that it does not hinder the employee to acquire the adequate maturity for the development of the task that the leader is directing.

With this attitude, the leader is acting in a way to motivate the team member, making him progress to maturity and acquire a maturity compatible with what he wants, that is, the delegation of tasks.

Maturity for work is described by technical ability, knowledge of the task to be performed. If the leader provides favourable conditions, he will be well directed. According to the theories of Drucker (1999), Hersey and Blanchard (1986), and Kolasa (1978), the maturity for the work concerns the confidence in oneself and the commitment associated with the technical capacity developed by the employee, that is, in order to have a high level of maturity it is necessary to have an overview of the context in which the employee is inserted, analyzing their psychological and work maturity.

So he decides how to act with the employee and, in return, he will be giving sustainability to the employee so that his development is adequate and growing.

This concept shows that the more the leader directs the relationship behaviour and the coach; not overloading it, the greater the motivation, acquiring confidence and thus, maturing, producing positive effects for the manager and the company.

Reflecting on this theory, the new item regarding communication can be elaborated. If there is a leader who makes decisions for his employee to mature, first, he must take care that the information is transmitted to him with the utmost clarity, in an attempt to boost his knowledge more quickly and effectively.

Communication

Communication is defined as the exchange of information between a transmitter and a receiver, together with the perception of meanings between the individuals involved for the real occurrence. Although communication has different ways of developing involving individuals, it occurs with the inclusion of 4 basic items for all:

- A source of information,
- A message,
- A receiver and an
- Interpretation of the message.

how the process occurs observing these four basic items.

Different ways of transmitting the message are found, which can be through symbols such as words, writing, drawing and many other forms, or the exchange of behaviours, such as gestures, eye contact, body language and other acts nonverbal.

In many cases, communication efforts are interrelated, both in symbols and in behaviour.

The main vision is to understand these symbols and behaviours.

The COMMUNICATION suggests that there is a distinction between the transmission of the communication and the understanding of the meaning of that information.

TRANSMISSION is handled by information theory, usually expressed in mathematical symbols and important in computer applications.

The main focus is the technical problem of transmitting a signal from one point to another, despite various interference that may affect it during transmission.

Thus, communication is seen as a mechanical process, dedicated to making a message reach a particular destination with a minimum of distortions and errors.

Although this is an overly simplified view of information theory, the key to the purposes is that, in this context, the accuracy of communication refers to the extent to which the basic signal transmitted by the sender is received, without distortion, by the RECEIVER.

Although information theory has played a vital role in solving many of the technical problems of transmitting signals through noisy channels, it cannot be applied literally to human communication.

The signal is affected by the amount of noise, static or errors in the system.

Thus, the communication will not be complete until the receiver has interpreted (perceived) the message, if the noise is too strong in relation to the signal, the message will not reach its destination, or it will arrive scrambled.

In this broader context, however, the accuracy of the communication refers to the extent to which the receiver is able to interpret (perceive) the signal in a manner consistent with the intent of the transmitter.

Considering that different people often give different meanings to things and events, the messages communicated are not always perceived as intended. Thus, differently from information theory, the different behavioural models of communication and the ways in which these meanings are interpreted. In this sense, communication is more complex than simply receiving a message without distortion.

The simple act of receiving the message does not guarantee that the receiver will interpret it correctly.

The MESSAGE is influenced by the information itself and the context. It must be considered: who is communicating and to whom, in terms of roles played; the language or symbol used and the ability to transmit the information and enable the understanding of the two parties; the channel used (written or spoken, for example); the content (considering the news, good or bad, relevant or irrelevant); interpersonal characteristics (trust, influence of the interlocutor); the context related to location, structure of information elaboration.

The communication can follow a description that begins with a source that is encoded to be transmitted. Then, the caller decides which channel is chosen.

Now, that choice may be the right one and even then there will be noises until it reaches the receiver. The information goes through the decoding to reach the recipient.

Then the communication happens: starting from the source, it is coded, the channel is chosen, the occurrence of noise, decoding and perception. Wanting to simplify the communication process as much as possible, it can be said that the cognitive material goes from the first to the last stage.

Real communication requires that, in its final stage, the state of the material is identical to what it presented in the first. Of course, a perfect match is unattainable in real life; however, the previous sentence emphasizes the need to seek to transmit the concepts, from the person who speaks until reaching the listener with a minimum of changes, in the case of communication through language.

Some difficulties in the transmission of information come from the presence of noise in the system. This term means more than the auditory dissonance that we used to call

"noise", although it includes it. In information terminology, noise means anything that interferes with the transmission process.

Although the existence of noise is more easily identified in the channel, or stage of the message, it can occur at any point in the communication process. Another feature of the process is that it can counteract noise. Redundancy is the transmission of more information than is necessary to ensure that the message supersedes the noise and is received.

According to Kolasa (1978, p. 262), a final aspect of communication, which plays a vital role in the transmission of information, is feedback.

As in other behaviour models, feedback is the information that returns from the outputs to serve as new inputs; doing so, changes or corrects the activity.

It allows the sender to know if your message is being received by the audience. In many cases too, false feedback can occur: for example, when a company president speaks to employees, they automatically shake their heads in agreement with the information conveyed, but that does not mean that they actually agree with what he is transmitting. This type of noise is called "false feedback".

The Communication Process

There are several ways to convey the message, which can be through symbols (words, writing, drawing, etc.) or changing behaviours (gestures, eye contact, body language and other non-verbal acts). In many cases, communication efforts are interrelated, both in symbols and in behaviour. The main vision is to understand these symbols and behaviours.

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Language and Communication

The importance of language and communication could never be overestimated in any exhibition on human behaviour.

No other factor puts the social and cognitive aspects of man in a better position than these two variables.

Communication between people is not only a characteristic of social beings: it is virtually necessary to ensure the continued functioning of a complex group, organization, or society.

To study communication, it is practically impossible not to show language as one of the most studied channels. It is a process that involves many steps, in which everything is not studied at the same time.

This fact makes it difficult for researchers to summarize the study as a whole. Often, the example that is given for communication is the verbal form (a set of written or spoken signs called the language).

However, the language can be non-verbal based on the context and the perception that each individual has of a situation or expression that occurred, as well as the visual stimuli to transmit information (for example, traffic light signalling), which in some cases can be considered more efficient than the speech or the writing itself.

Verbal communication also includes more than spoken or written words. Other types of written signs are verbal, as is the case with mathematical "signs" and Portuguese itself, speaking of patterns of ideas.

Kolasa (1978) explains why the term "sign" is used instead of "symbol": "... the term" sign "was preferred to" symbol "in reaction to the element of communication that represents something from reality.

This is because many researchers in communication prefer to reserve the use of the word "symbol" for certain broader cultural aspects, such as flag, cross, Wall Street and other representations or associations used by a society. »

With the study of language, it is possible to verify the interest in certain approaches, such as the study of the concept of «semiotics» (study of signals that transmit information).

Language is only a part of the various forms of sign communication known. It can be verbal or non-verbal and can be divided into three different areas: semantics, syntax and pragmatics.

The first is responsible for the relationships between the signals.

In the syntax it can be verified that it handles the signals with each other.

Pragmatics deals with the use of signs. For the communication to develop correctly or at least with a lower percentage of failures, it can be achieved by analyzing the communication transmission skills.

The possible part of finding a more suitable form goes through some steps, such as:

- In the use of language, choose the most appropriate and direct form, not using complicated forms if there are efficient simplified forms, without using jargon;
- Provide clear and complete information when possible;
- Transmit information in an appropriate environment without the interruptions that usually occur in companies, mainly;
- If feasible, make use of the various senses such as auditory or visual; make face-to-face communication to have greater effects.

Interpersonal communication

For Bowditch (1992) "communication is essentially an interactive and didactic process (from person to person)". Communication is built by meanings that develop expectations about the experiences lived individually by the interlocutor or transmitter, allowing them to exchange meanings among themselves. This is a process that can be called transactional for the construction of meanings.

For this process to occur, four basic functions for interpersonal communication are mentioned:

- 1) Control to clarify rules and responsibilities;
- 2) Information to propose the base to decide and execute orders;
- 3) Motivation to influence others to achieve the goal; and
- 4) Emotion to express feelings.

Organizational communication

In the organizational view of the studies carried out by Bowditch (1992), communication can be analyzed in three broad functions:

- 1) Production and control to achieve the objective of production;
- 2) Innovation in order to help adapt to the environment; and
- 3) Socialization and maintenance, that is, the means of carrying out the work and for personal involvement with it and with other people, promoting motivation.

Data, Information and Knowledge

Data, information and knowledge are fundamental elements for communication and decision making in organizations, but the respective meanings are not so evident.

They form a hierarchical system that is difficult to define.

What is given to an individual may be information and / or knowledge for another. Davenport (1998) corroborates this point of view, resisting making this distinction, considering it clearly imprecise.

Considering the interrelation and the difficult possibility of clearly separating what is given, information and knowledge, and aware of its importance for the decision, it seeks to mark out the meanings. Data are raw, meaningless elements, disconnected from reality.

According to Davenport (1998), they are "observations about the state of the world". They are symbols and images that do not dispel uncertainties. They are the raw material for information. Poor quality data leads to information and decisions of the same nature.

Given that data is considered the raw material for information: what is information? Information is given with meaning. "They are data endowed with relevance and purpose" (Drucker apud Davenport, 1998).

But what is knowledge?

For Davenport (1998), "knowledge is the most valuable information (...) it is valuable precisely because someone gave information a context, a meaning, an interpretation (...)". Knowledge can then be considered as information processed by individuals. The value added to the information depends on the previous knowledge of these individuals.

Therefore, knowledge is acquired through the use of information in actions. In this way, knowledge cannot be separated from the individual; it is strictly related to its perception, which encodes, decodes, distorts and uses information according to its personal characteristics, that is, according to its mental models.

The concept of knowledge has a more complex meaning than that of information. Knowing is a process of understanding and internalizing the information received, possibly combining it in order to generate more knowledge.

When considering the interrelation between the three elements and carrying out the analysis, they can infer that the data alone does not mean useful knowledge for decision making, constituting only the beginning of the process.

The great challenge for decision makers is to transform data into information and information into knowledge, minimizing individual interference in this transformation process.

Transforming Data into Information and Knowledge

Providing data, information and knowledge of meaning is not as simple as it seems. Individual characteristics, which form the mental model of each person, interfere in the encoding / decoding of these elements, often causing individual distortions that may cause problems in the communication process.

According to Davenport (1998), to mitigate these distortions, one must be aware that there are differences:

- Between what is meant and what is actually said;
- Between what is said and what others hear;
- Between what they hear and what they hear;
- Between what they understand and remember;
- Between what they remember and relay;
- People only listen to what they want and how they want it, according to their own experiences, paradigms and pre-judgments;
- There is information that individuals do not notice and do not see;
- Information they see and don't care about;
- Information they see, and don't understand or don't decode;
- Information they see and use; information they seek; guessing information;
- Mood and mood can affect the way information is handled;
- Informational approaches usually favour the rational, sequential and analytical attributes of information and its management, to the detriment of others equally important (if not more), such as those related to intuitive and non-linear approaches.

The apprehension of information is a superior cognitive function that takes place in the context of language.

Whenever one wants to apprehend more information about the context in which they are inserted, one has to expand the perceptual skills, because the way of life induces a

perceptual narrowing and a restricted and fragmented worldview and that people's needs in relation to information changes constantly because perception, in addition to being individual, is contingent.

Therefore, the decision-maker must be aware that the biggest challenge is not to obtain data, information and knowledge, but the acceptance that, in the encoding / decoding process, distortions occur and that there are ways to soften them.

One can exemplify people's interference in encoding, decoding and distortion in the transformation of data into information and information into knowledge by the following example.

Different people facing the same fact tend to interpret it according to their mental models, which lead them to perceive it differently. For example: a BMW3 car, the latest model, convertible, zero kilometres, totally destroyed in an accident in which the driver hit a centennial tree knocking it over can be encoded, decoded and distorted in the following ways.

Some people will be led to decode the information based on their material values: «Soon such an expensive car! Does he have insurance? »Other people, with sharper human values, will focus on the human being: « Did the accident result in injuries? »Other people with ecological interests will focus their attention on the fate of the centennial tree: «Right on this tree! Couldn't it have been in another one? ». Being aware of these and much other interference in the demands with data, information and knowledge in the decision-making process is the first step to mitigate them.

Boosting Decisions

In the decision-making process, it is important to have data, information and knowledge available, but these are usually dispersed, fragmented and stored in the minds of individuals and suffer interference from their mental models.

At this point, the communication process and teamwork play important roles in solving some of the essential difficulties in the decision-making process.

Through the communication process, it is possible to seek consensus that will make it possible to foresee the adequacy of individual action plans according to the conviction and not the imposition or manipulation.

Through teamwork, it is possible to obtain the greatest amount of information and perspectives for different analyzes, with the most convincing proposal being validated in the argumentative confrontation of the others.

To boost the quality of organizational decisions, a reflection on improving communication and involving people in decision-making is suggested.

Improve communication

Some management theorists, such as Davenport (1998), Nonaka & Takeuchi (1997), point to a new direction for communication, focusing mainly on issues related to the transmission of information and organizational knowledge.

The concepts of data, information and knowledge are strictly related to their usefulness in the decision-making process and linked to the concept of communication.

The communication process is a sequence of events in which data, information and knowledge are transmitted from a sender to a receiver.

According to Davenport (1998), one of the characteristics of information is the difficulty of its transfer with absolute fidelity, and, since knowledge is information with value, consequently, transmission is even more difficult.

Information is valuable precisely because someone gave it a context, a meaning, added its own wisdom, and considered its broader implications, generating knowledge. Knowledge, therefore, is tacit and difficult to explain. «Whoever has tried to transfer knowledge between people or groups knows how difficult the task is. Recipients must not only use the information, but also recognize that it does constitute knowledge »(Nonaka apud Davenport, 1998).

To improve the quality of communication, human beings need to develop the skills to express themselves and to listen.

Usually people are predisposed to defend their opinions.

Thus, when one interlocutor speaks, the other is not aware of what he says, but he is already preparing the argument to defend his opinion on the subject, interfering with the quality of communication.

Communicative action really occurs when people, free from self-defence, try to reach an agreement on a certain decision situation, listening and respecting other opinions.

A group of people, with intellectual preparation, information and interest in reaching an agreement, discusses all possible alternatives, until they constitute a consensual collective action plan.

This process goes from the norms of education to the absence of pathological deviations that may impede the perception of the general meaning of a discussion or the personal review of behaviours and concepts when confronted with different arguments.

Thus, people start to contribute in the field of decisions when they manage, in the process of dialogue, to put themselves in the place of the other and perceive, from this new perspective, their reasons and interests), becoming it is essential to highlight the importance of maturity as an essential element in organizational communication for decision making.

The decision is thus considered a linguistic system, an essentially collective process in which the multi-rationality or anti-rationality prevails characterized by the interference of individual differences in the collection and interpretation of information, making it impossible to have only one decision, "the right one".

If there is no single alternative for a given decision situation, where does rationality lie?

In order to reduce individual interferences, one of the suggested paths is that of a team decision.

Involvement of people in the decision

Decision-making in organizations will increasingly require teamwork and greater participation by people.

Teamwork highlights the dialogue procedures based on the idea that, in an organization, communication should be stimulated with a view to establishing a common thought.

The establishment of a common thought consists in considering the point of view of each one, so that the decisions made in the organizations have a higher quality level.

The decision-making process then moves from the individual level to the team level.

Considering that no person has all the organizational information and knowledge and that this information and knowledge is not always made explicit and available, making each one hold only a part of them, team decision making is a way to be used to overcome the barriers to information and partial knowledge.

Decision making involving a larger number of people tends to result in more qualified results, increasing the knowledge of the decision situation, mitigating, through the aggregation of information and knowledge, the distortions of the individualized view.

Decisions made by heterogeneous teams, composed of women, men, youth, the elderly, tend to result in higher quality.

People with different points of view and experiences also decode the decision situation differently. Listening to and trying to understand these visions improves decisions.

Team decisions tend to be more solid than individual decisions, although they usually require more time. When it comes to decision making and especially team decision making, we cannot fail to consider the role that technology plays.

Technology as support

Technology plays an essential role both in the communication and storage of data, information and knowledge and in the integration of decision makers. It also has enormous potential for knowledge sharing.

From anywhere in the world, the decision maker can reach out to and learn from other people's past experience.

The exchange of information and knowledge and the respective quality and speed are at the heart of the success of organizations.

The greater the capacity of information and communication technologies, the greater the capacity for interrelationships and the ability to learn and profit from the sharing of information and knowledge.

At the same time that they lead to an increase in the capacity to share information and knowledge, they also make it possible to increase their available quantities, which is, above all, an increase in raw data, of which only a part becomes potential information, which means that only a small number of them will become information or knowledge.

The constant increase in the volume of information and knowledge has been an increasing difficulty in moments of decision.

The executive of the beginning of the century made decisions based on the scarcity of information.

Nowadays, the executive is faced with an increasing amount of information available. Buried in a sea of data, information and knowledge, executives must develop skills and competences to separate the "wheat from the chaff", because for information and knowledge to be considered useful, they must be understood and used by the decision maker.

Representation of Elements in Decision Making

Understanding what is given, information and knowledge and its interrelationships with the communication and decision processes with the elements involved in decision making, which seeks to incite the discussion that data, information and knowledge must be seen as a value-adding chain and that they are essential elements for decision-making and, therefore, should not be confined to the head of organizational individuals, but shared through a well-established communication system.

The analysis of the elements involved in decision-making is not intended to end the discussion regarding decision-making in organizations, in view of its complexity.

There is no perfect formula for making correct decisions in the company. In the traditional organization, decisions are made by a decision-making elite that perpetuates itself in power through a broad process of alliances, causing distance from macro-objectives and loss of information.

Communicative management, in turn, is based on communicative action, which consists of the discursive formation of the will, through the debate between intact subjectivities, in conditions close to the ideal.

An essential element in this decision-making process is the expectation of mature individual behaviour, both social and moral. The result is a confrontation between the avoidable and inevitable complexity of traditional and communicative models of management. Information and technology have been going together since computers became commercial equipment in the 1960s.

In the first stage, the use of computers was limited to high-speed operations, previously performed manually.

New tools and methodologies have emerged since then, in the search for improvement of systems that started to gain more and more importance, however, there are items to be properly organized so that the computer system can express what the creators wanted, as is the case with information and data that present concepts that differ and therefore this differentiation is often not clear, causing difficulties for the system user.

The data used by the system can be defined as "a formal abstraction that can be represented and transformed by a computer" (SETZER, 1999).

We can understand the data as a purely syntactic mathematical entity, which can be represented by formal structures and descriptions.

Representations of numbers and words are easily stored on a digital machine, using binary conventions and patterns associated with numbers and characters. Information is an informal abstraction and therefore cannot be represented mathematically or by any logical theory.

A report, an image or a diagram are examples of information, as they have meanings for the people who read them. Individual perception is a factor that particularizes the understanding of information.

The concept of information is not accurate, as it involves abstractions and perceptions on the part of people who are reading the information itself.

Conclusion

The perception, being particularized, allows the message to be properly interpreted so that there is an appropriate transformation for the information; however, if the reading is done in a team, the perception of an individual will not predominate, at the moment of making the decision, thus making it possible to organize an impartial decision making.

References

Argyris Chris On Organizational Learning. Wiley-Blackwell (first published January 1st 1993

Behn, R.D. and J.W. Vaupel. 1982. Quick Analysis for Busy Decision Makers. Basic Books, Inc. New York, NY. 415pp.

Bromiley, Philip, and Devaki Rau. "Strategic Decision Making." In APA Handbook of Industrial and Organizational Psychology. Vol. 1, Building and Developing the Organization. Edited by Sheldon Zedeck, 161–182. Washington, DC: American Psychological Association, 2011.

Cray, David, Geoffrey R. Mallory, Richard J. Butler, David J. Hickson, and David C. Wilson. "Explaining Decision Processes." *Journal of Management Studies* 28.3 (1991): 227–251.

Drucker Peter. *Managing for the Future*. Routledge London and NY. Kolasa Blair . *Ideology: The Basis for Executive Decisions at a National Level*

Mintzberg, Henry, and James Waters. "Of Strategies, Deliberate and Emergent." *Strategic Management Journal* 6.3 (1985): 257–272.

Nonaka, I. and Takeuchi, H. (1995). *The knowledge-creating company*, New York, Oxford: Oxford University Press

Tannenbaum Robert. *How to Choose a Leadership Pattern*. Harvard Business Review 1973

Taylor James *Decision Management Systems*. IBM Press.

Friedman, V.J., Lipshitz, R. and Overmeer, W. (2001). „Creating conditions for organizational learning“. In Dierkes, M., Antal, A.B., Child, J. and Nonaka, I. (Eds), Handbook of organizational learning and knowledge. Oxford: Oxford University Press,